

FROM CODE TO COBALT:

TOWARD A SUPPLY CHAIN-AWARE THEORY OF AI LIFECYCLES

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THE PROBLEM

AI is often treated as software. But it depends on raw materials (lithium, cobalt, silicon), components (semiconductors and GPUs), servers and cooling systems, data centers and electricity, continuous retraining and scaling, and requires end-of-life hardware management.

Why Current Approaches Fall Short

- “Green AI” focuses governance on model training efficiency
- Yet efficiency gains may lower costs, expand demand, and increase total use (Jevons paradox)
- Most **frameworks (OECD, ISO, NIST) remain software-centric**, emphasizing design, deployment, and monitoring while under-addressing: **supply chains, infrastructure, lifecycle impacts, sustainability trade-offs**

RQ: How can AI governance better account for sustainability across the full AI lifecycle?

THE POLICY CONTEXT

Initial mapping of key EU policy instruments: AI Act | Data Act | EED | CSRD | CRMA

Four structural gaps:

1. **externalized impacts** - sustainability governed indirectly via adjacent policy domains (e.g., energy regulation, hardware policy, and corporate reporting)
2. **lifecycle fragmentation** - no mechanism tracks impacts across lifecycle phases or evaluates trade-offs between them
3. **rebound blind spots** - efficiency gains may increase adoption and compute demand, potentially offsetting environmental benefits
4. **weak procurement levers** - sustainability criteria remain weakly standardized or enforceable

➔ **Result: sustainability remains fragmented rather than embedded in AI governance**

OUR PROPOSAL: A SUPPLY-CHAIN AWARE AI LIFECYCLE

AI as a materially embedded sociotechnical system linking:

- **software** (models, algorithms);
- **hardware** (chips, servers);
- **infrastructure** (data centers, energy systems);
- **organizational decisions** (deployment, scaling)

Design Principles:

- **material embeddedness** - systems are linked to physical infrastructures and resource flows, causing impacts beyond computation;
- **lifecycle continuity** - sustainability impacts are distributed across phases, requiring governance mechanisms that span design, deployment, operation, and disposal;
- **iterative dynamics** - monitoring triggers retraining, deployment decisions affect infrastructure demand, and efficiency gains influence scaling behaviour;
- **sociotechnical integration** - organizational practices (model selection, procurement, scaling decisions) are treated as integral components shaping sustainability

GOVERNANCE GAPS AND IMPLICATIONS

Evidence base: policy analysis + 10 interviews

Three systemic gaps

1. **upstream obscenity:** raw materials, semiconductors, hardware impacts remain weakly visible in AI governance
2. **cross-phase fragmentation:** no mechanism tracks sustainability across stages
3. **dynamic blind spots:** efficiency gains may increase total footprint (Jevons' paradox)

Implications

- for policymakers: extend governance beyond model risk; include lifecycle criteria
- for organizations: sustainable procurement; govern scaling decisions
- for researchers: connect AI governance with supply chains

Next steps

- develop a comprehensive sustainable AI governance framework spanning supply chains and the full AI lifecycle
- validate lifecycle impacts, governance gaps, and organizational practices across sectors
- translate findings into metrics, procurement criteria, and policy tools

RESPONSIBLE AI GOVERNANCE MUST BE LIFECYCLE- AND SUPPLY-CHAIN AWARE